

1 **HOTAIRM1 is repressed in breast cancer but becomes activated upon engineered trastuzumab**
2 **resistance in HER2+ breast cancer cells.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We describe here expression of the Hox locus non-coding RNA HOTAIRM1 in human breast cancer. In
8 primary tumors from humans with cancer, HOTAIRM1 expression was repressed. Expression of a mutant
9 oncogene (KRas G12V) in human cells could activate HOTAIRM1. In an in vitro cellular system designed
10 to study resistance to trastuzumab we found activation of HOTAIRM1. The significance of HOTAIRM1
11 activation in resistance settings in cancer cells is not yet understood.

12 Citations

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